

HOW VIRTUAL REALITY HELPS STUDENTS LEARN ICT BETTER AT GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS IN SRI LANKA

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Abstract: Education in Sri Lanka is free and it contains some important factors to understand, information following interaction is significant in Sri Lankan education system. However, information communication about technique specific stock and its whole benefit will spread via discussions strolling. This section covers information about the impact of method on articles, websites, considerations, and other topics in education. Furthermore, in schools, the usage of technology is increasing, as seen in this section. This section contains information on the information communication application, its benefits, information communication techniques, and plans to coordinate instruction about experiences will be utilized technology. Worldwide profession approach of application experiences will observe when, usually they are the following inside the headings.

Keywords: Virtual Reality, Learning outcome, inclusive education, collaboration

Introduction

In the Department of Education in the twenty-first century Information communication should be appropriately used throughout transition to improve students' lives. Government school education might undergo a change thanks to virtual reality (VR), especially when it comes to teaching information and communication technology (ICT) [1-3]. When computers and websites are used properly, information communication technology offers both instructors and students a useful opportunity. This new approach to education involves having teachers and students concentrate their learning. Application technique for the profession of information communication There are several new techniques and resources available for students to utilize. The circumstances as outlined in the Education Setting Up are plausible. The use of information communication techniques and basic education to learn how much has made prediction more challenging. due to the small scale of the research project being conducted. First School on the rating system Technique of Information Communication adhered to these studies [4-6].

For universities to go for people who are unable to master Information Communication Techniques through education, an opportunity to gain confidence has been provided. The students who are comparing will see when this is explained. VR delivers an immersive learning environment that holds students' attention. Instead of passively receiving information from textbooks or lectures, students may actively participate in ICT topics via interactive VR simulations and apps.

Experiential Learning

Under the correct conditions, experience may be a valuable source of learning. However, if certain requirements are not met, the learning may be inaccurate. This chapter aims to define the components of "experiential learning" and specify the circumstances required for "proper"

learning. Although most pedagogies allow for some experiential learning, this article aims to identify techniques that are more likely to encourage it.

Virtual reality helps students to have personal familiarity with ICT topics. In a secure and regulated environment, kids may study computer networks, interact with virtual computer systems, and troubleshoot software bugs. This hands-on approach improves knowledge and retention when compared to standard teaching approaches [7].

Engagement and Collective Learning

Conventional theories of how groups learn are challenged by the patterned, relational, and emergent nature of learning. Examples of these theories include the analysis of group properties or outcomes, as in theories of team performance, the linear progression of competence, as in communities of practice, or the use of activity theory to resolve contradictions in activity systems. We come to the conclusion that, although drawing on both specific and non-specific elements that can only be attained via practice, collective learning is an all-encompassing relational complex that cannot be reduced to the sum of its parts.

Information Communication Professional Technique Using formal learning, students, instructors, and professionals are encouraged to discuss their places and eligibility in an unpredictable manner. Various cultural differences among sects to become accustomed to the opportunities that a cause provides. As a result of Karporu's Consensus Comment, Information Parimarik will require more assistance. Further education learning is carried out for a specific amount of time, regardless of whether the living term is complete.

Information Communication The impact of a technique in education depends on how and why it is utilized. Other education will study technologies, tools, and examples such as information communication techniques for everyone, Ella, and places. Only one model does not operate [8, 9].

Visualization is crucial for understanding complex ICT ideas that traditional teaching techniques may struggle to convey. Virtual reality allows students to visualize abstract ideas like algorithms, data structures, and programming logic in three dimensions. This graphic depiction helps students have a better understanding of ICT fundamentals [10-12].

Quality-raising and inclusive

VR can suit a variety of learning methods and preferences, making it a valuable teaching tool for students with varying needs and talents. Whether students are visual, auditory, or kinesthetic learners, VR can deliver a tailored learning experience to fit their specific needs. Radio and television have had an impact due to education in broadcasting. The complete study was not done. Although, a little bit carried out a systematic study of the findings according to normal school education. This moment to resemble to know is approaching. By this strategy, pupils' marks appear to have increased in the coming days of school [13, 14].

On the contrary, Math application, website, and it is related to approaches by application, in learning progress has occurred that is considered. But this is About Comment, and the poor win. of the computer by application, might be of the curriculum. Usability has increased. Many studies report. Specifically, research have shown that when a computer is utilized in classes by a teacher, students score higher in terms of getting help. Students are studying at a rapid pace. Will's learning capacity is improving. When students use computers, they get more excited about studying. There are many results, however there are also some shortcomings, as stated [15,16].

Computer application, Website, Dependent Techniques, and Teacher Training are also used to research best environments and assist with tasks. This study covers everything and is open to critique. It is stated that there are several shortcomings. Correct point Details Absence decreases. Students' and instructors' opinions are exchanged, and education in learning is beneficial. Change will come, as the saying goes. Computer and Internet of Sites App Karporai will centrally assess the education environment when forecasting a problem; now, metrics cannot be used in practice. In addition, you will study deliberately, technically, and practically. Because of this, you will be able to correct the tough learning process. In learning, there is a need for change, techniques, and a conclusion that something cannot be done [17-19].

Accessibility

Education is a fascinating example as it is expected to make extensive use of ICT. A description of the connections between technologies for accessibility and education is examined through the use of scenarios in three distinct contexts: a class using the technologies that are currently in use, a class using all available technologies, and a third scenario where the learning environment is an intelligent environment. The comparison draws attention to the disparities between technology, accessibility issues, and methods for resolving them.

Many government schools have minimal resources, such as poor ICT infrastructure and qualified staff. VR can help to close this gap by enabling students to access high-quality educational content and simulations regardless of their geographical location or resource availability [20,21].

Personalized Learning

A PLE may be thought of as an online representation of a learner's informal learning practices. Peer support and peer networks have always been essential for learners to assist their learning. These peer networks manifest themselves in the real world as study groups, brown bag meetings, student organizations, lunchtime talks, and communities of practice. Up until recently, there was no efficient way to simulate these unstructured learning experiences virtually. The Web is becoming less of a vast information warehouse and more of a place where people interact thanks to recent advancements in social networking.

VR apps may be tailored to students' individual learning needs and interests. Teachers may track their students' progress, identify areas of weakness, and provide targeted support and criticism. This personalized technique improves learning outcomes and ensures that students get the assistance they need to succeed [22,23]. VR technology enables collaborative learning by allowing students to cooperate on projects and solve problems in virtual worlds. Collaborative learning promotes communication, teamwork, and peer-to-peer assistance, all of which are necessary abilities for success in the ICT area [24, 25].

VR simulations may simulate real-world ICT scenarios, including cybersecurity, software development, and network infrastructure architecture. By participating in these simulations, students develop practical skills and information that are directly useful to their future jobs in technology. [26-30]

Conclusion

It can be concluded that the VR delivers an immersive learning environment that holds students' attention. Instead of passively receiving information from textbooks or lectures, students may actively participate in ICT topics via interactive VR simulations and apps.

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